

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for Alsin (UniProt ID: Q96Q42) for use in western blot

Vera Ruíz Moleón¹, Sara González Bolívar¹, Riham Ayoubi¹, Peter S. McPherson¹ and Carl Laflamme^{1*},
and NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group

¹ Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Structural Genomics Consortium, The Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

* Corresponding author: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca

Abstract

Alsin is a guanine nucleotide exchange factor (GEF) involved in membrane trafficking and axon development. Here we have characterized six Alsin commercial antibodies for western blot using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

Q96Q42, *ALS2*, Alsin, Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis 2 protein, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

Alsin is a 184 kDa protein encoded by the *ALS2* gene. It contains three putative GEF domains: regulator of chromosome condensation 1 (RCC1) like domains (termed RLD), a diffuse B cell lymphoma (Dbl) homology/pleckstrin homology (DH/PH) domain, and a vacuolar protein sorting 9 (VPS9) domain. By acting as a guanine nucleotide exchange factor (GEF), Alsin regulates endocytosis, membrane trafficking and axon development (1). Mutations in the *ALS2* gene are associated with the early-onset amyotrophic lateral sclerosis 2 (ALS2) (2).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (3). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein (3). Here we characterized six commercial Alsin antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of Alsin properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (4) and in Table 4 of this data note (3).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells (5, 6). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (7). The HAP1 expresses the *ALS2* transcript at $4.0 \log_2$ TPM+1, and an *ALS2* KO HAP1 cell line was obtained from Horizon Discovery (Table 1). Moreover, as seen on DepMap, the HAP1 does not carry mutations in the *ALS2* that could affect antibody–epitope binding.

To screen the six antibodies by western blot, WT and *ALS2* KO protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with all six Alsin antibodies in parallel (Figure 1).

In conclusion, we have screened six Alsin commercial antibodies in western blot by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human HAP1 WT and *ALS2* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 4 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform (7). High-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect Alsin were identified. Researchers who wish to study Alsin in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available Alsin antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in Alsin, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. Alsin experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (3). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

The cell lines, primary and secondary antibodies used in this study are listed in Table 1, 2, and 3, respectively. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) (8, 9). All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Antibody screening by western blot

HAP1 WT and ALS2 KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Dataset for the Alsin antibody screening study <DOI>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGH007913c008	CVCL_C7HG	HAP1	ALS2 KO

Table 2: Summary of the Alsin antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab170896**	1043454-12	AB_2885099	recombinant mono	EPR11185	rabbit	0.10	Wb, IP
ABclonal	A7125	3561311005	AB_2767680	polyclonal	-	rabbit	2.01	Wb, IF
Abnova	H00057679-M01*	08291-4F9	AB_464385	monoclonal	4F9	mouse	0.50	Wb
Abnova	H00057679-M02*	08200-4F10	AB_1203950	monoclonal	4F10	mouse	0.50	Wb, IF
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP57487_P050	QC28435-40386	AB_10641558	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-61254	VL3152380C	AB_2637895	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.10	IF, IP

Wb=western blot; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF= immunofluorescence, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.5

Table 4: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in western blot

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Figure 1: Alsins antibody screening by western blot

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: Alsin antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of HAP1 WT and *ALS2* KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated Alsin antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab170896** at 1/1000, A7125 at 1/500, H00057679-M01* at 1/1000, H00057679-M02* at 1/1000, ARP57487 at 1/500, PA5-61254 at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 183.6 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.